

Development Strategies For Beef Cattle Farming in the Solidarity of Alumni Indonesian People's School of Animal Husbandry (SASPRI) in South Dolo Sub-District Sigi Regency

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Abstract: The development of livestock businesses is aimed at increasing food security and increasing people's purchasing power through increasing income. In order to achieve this goal, the strategy used is to increase active community participation, encourage investment in livestock businesses in rural areas and empower livestock farming communities. This research aims to analyze the internal and external factors of livestock business development strategies, formulate strategies for developing beef cattle farming businesses, and formulate strategic priorities for developing beef cattle farming businesses in the Indonesian People's Animal Husbandry School Alumni Solidarity (SASPRI) South Dolo District, Sigi Regency. This research was carried out in the month April–June 2023. This research method uses the Case Study method using SWOT analysis and QSPM analysis. The informants selected were 8 beef cattle breeders. The research results on the EFI matrix assessment were 2.512 and the EFE matrix was 2.26 so the business position located in cell V where stocks like this are best managed with hold and maintain strategies. Strategies that can be carried out based on SWOT analysis are properly maintain existing resources to increase beef cattle productivity to meet local supply needs. Increase knowledge about processing livestock waste products which can provide profitable income.

Keywords: Beef Cattle, SWOT Analysis, QSPM, Beef Cattle Business Development Strategy, SASPRI.

I. INTRODUCTION

The development of livestock businesses is aimed at increasing food security and increasing people's purchasing power through increasing income. In order to achieve this goal, the strategy used is to increase active community participation, encourage investment in livestock businesses in rural areas and empower livestock farming communities (Karim, 2019).

Several efforts have been made by the local government to increase the population through the use of technology, but to date these efforts have not been able to meet the welfare level of breeders if we look at the income received by breeders. This can be seen from the ability to cultivate beef cattle, which is mostly still done as a side business with a very simple and scattered maintenance system. The new ownership scale reaches 1 to 3 heads per farmer. To increase the business structure to become a main business branch, breeders are still faced with management and capital problems. To increase business volume, breeders require relatively large additional costs.

Central Sulawesi is an agricultural area that is very supportive of the growth and development of the agricultural sector, including the livestock subsector. Development that can have a direct impact is development that can increase farmers' income through beef cattle farming. Beef cattle are a form of livestock whose main production is meat, bones and skin (Suratyah, 2009).

Beef cattle are a leading commodity in Sigi Regency, based on the average development of beef cattle in Sigi Regency in 2018-2021 showing positive results, namely 12.18%. If we look at market demand, it can be said that beef cattle are much sought after as the Eid al-Adha holiday approaches to be used as sacrificial animals (BPS Sigi Regency 2021). This is an opportunity to encourage farmers in South Dolo District, Sigi Regency, who are small-scale farmers to raise cattle, and even have the potential to develop beef cattle in South Dolo District, namely the Indonesian People's Animal Husbandry School Alumni Solidarity (SASPRI).

The People's Animal Husbandry School (SPR) was declared in 2018, then declared passed by the assessment team in 2021, so that SPR changed its name to Indonesian People's Animal Husbandry School Alumni Solidarity (SASPRI) with the aim of being a means of transferring knowledge and technology to build livestock awareness and encourage collective action for small-scale breeders, both individuals and those who have joined groups or associations, is encouraged to consolidate to build a collective company that is managed professionally under one management. This is an effort to make breeders sovereign and have a higher bargaining position.

Overall, the number of beef cattle at the Indonesian People's Animal Husbandry School Alumni Solidarity (SASPRI) is approximately 334 head of cattle in 2021. Public demand for beef is quite high, especially on religious holidays. The ever-increasing demand for beef cattle has not been able to be met by SASPRI because the availability of beef cattle is still small, due to limited land, capital, weak support from outside parties, which is one of the obstacles in addition to the cattle fattening process which takes a relatively long time.

Facing such situations and conditions, in order to optimize the utilization of the potential resources of the beef cattle business in order to support the development and improvement of animal husbandry and the standard of living of breeders, therefore efforts are needed to identify strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats as material for consideration in the context of determining alternative strategies and strategic priorities for developing beef cattle farming in the Indonesian People's Animal Husbandry School Alumni Solidarity (SASPRI) South Dolo District, Sigi Regency.

II. RESEARCH METHODS

Research Location and Time

This research was carried out at the Solidarity Alumni of the Indonesian People's Animal Husbandry School (SASPRI) South Dolo District, Sigi Regency from April to June 2023. The location for this research was chosen based on the consideration that there is a large population of beef cattle in the Solidarity Alumni of the Indonesian People's Animal Husbandry School, South Dolo District, Regency. Sigi.

Type and Source of data

The type of data used in this research regarding the strategy for developing the Beef Cattle livestock business in the Indonesian People's Animal Husbandry School Alumni Solidarity (SASPRI) South Dolo District, Sigi Regency is by using qualitative data.

The data sources used in this research are:

- a. Primary data is data obtained directly from interviews or surveys using a list of questions (questionnaire) that has been prepared previously to obtain data about strategies for developing beef cattle farming businesses.
- b. Secondary data is data that is already available so researchers only need to search and collect data. Secondary data is generally used to support primary data, and researchers must select quality and appropriate data. Secondary data was obtained from the Sigi Regency Livestock Service, Sigi Regency Central Statistics Agency (BPS),

Data collection technique

The data collection techniques used in this research are:

1. Observation is carrying out direct observations in the beef cattle farming business at the Indonesian People's Animal Husbandry School Alumni Solidarity (SASPRI) South Dolo District, Sigi Regency.
2. Interviews are data collection carried out through direct interviews with informants based on a list of questions (questionnaire) that has been prepared previously.
3. Documentation is by taking notes and taking pictures at the research location, precisely at the Indonesian People's Animal Husbandry School Alumni Solidarity (SASPRI) South Dolo District, Sigi Regency.

Research Methods

The method used in this research is a case study at the Indonesian Animal Husbandry School Alumni Solidarity (SASPRI) South Dolo District, Sigi Regency. Case study is a research method that carries out an in-depth examination of a situation called a case using systematic methods, in observation, collecting information data and reporting research data.

Determination of Respondents

The respondents used in this research were people who were considered to have in-depth knowledge of the conditions of the beef cattle farming business in the Indonesian People's Animal Husbandry School Alumni Solidarity (SASPRI) South Dolo District, Sigi Regency. The respondents used as data sources for this research were 8 SASPRI administrators.

Data analysis technique

Data analysis is a research process that is carried out after all the data needed to solve the problem under study has been obtained with complete clarity and certainty. The use of analytical tools really determines the accuracy of drawing conclusions therefore data analysis activities are activities that cannot be ignored in the research process. This research will use qualitative data analysis techniques and use the SWOT analysis method.

Internal and external environmental data will be processed using non-statistical methods, namely the EFI, EFE and SWOT Matrix analysis tools. To answer the first, second and third research objectives in processing this data analysis, it is to describe the results of observations of the company's internal and external environment based on questionnaires and literature search results.

Operational Definition

The operational definition used in this research is:

1. The development strategy is an effort to improve technical, theoretical and conceptual skills in the context of developing the beef cattle business at the Indonesian People's Animal Husbandry School Alumni Solidarity (SASPRI) South Dolo District, Sigi Regency.
2. The breeder population is beef cattle breeders who know and are directly involved in activities to increase the beef cattle population in the Indonesian People's Animal Husbandry School Alumni Solidarity (SASPRI) South Dolo District, Sigi Regency.
3. Breeders are people/groups who cultivate beef cattle in the Indonesian People's Animal Husbandry School Alumni Solidarity (SASPRI) South Dolo District, Sigi Regency.
4. Internal factors, namely the strengths and weaknesses that influence the improvement/development of beef cattle in the Indonesian People's Animal Husbandry School Alumni Solidarity (SASPRI) South Dolo District, Sigi Regency.
5. External factors are opportunities and threats that influence the development of beef cattle farming businesses in the Indonesian People's Animal Husbandry School Alumni Solidarity (SASPRI) South Dolo District, Sigi Regency.
6. SWOT analysis is an analysis to identify weaknesses and strengths, opportunities and threats to formulate strategies that can be used.
7. The QSPM matrix is an analysis to determine strategic priorities in developing beef cattle farming businesses, and is used to evaluate and select the best strategy that best suits the external and internal environment.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Eval Matrix Analysis of Internal Strategy Factors

Table 4.2 Internal Strategy Factor Evaluation Matrix

No	Internal Strategic Factors (Strengths)	Weight	Rating	Mark
1	Breeding experience	0.095	2.87	0.272
2	Good quality beef cattle	0.088	3.12	0.274
3	Short distribution channels	0.099	2.75	0.272
4	Availability of feed land	0.077	2.25	0.173
5	Breeder education (Nonformal)	0.114	4.00	0.456
6	Potential natural resources owned	0.081	2.87	0.232
Sub Total		0.554		1.679
<i>(Weakness)</i>				
1	There is no processing of waste products	0.117	1.87	0.218
2	Access to technology and technological development is still low	0.102	2.75	0.280
3	Limited capital	0.123	1.87	0.230
4	The time for cultivating livestock is quite long	0.094	1.12	0.105
Sub Total		0.436		0.833
Total Nilai (Sub Total I + Sub Total II)		1		2.512

Source: Processed primary data, 2023

Strength is given by rating on a major scale of 4 to a minor scale of 1 and Each weakness is given a rating of 1 to 4 based on the results of interviews with beef cattle farm owners. The result of multiplying the weight and rating is a score for the business's strengths and weaknesses. Total strength and weakness value 2,512.

2. Eval Matrix Analysis of External Strategy Factors

Table 4.3 External Strategy Factor Evaluation Matrix

No	External Strategic Factors (Opportunities)	Weight	Rating	Mark
1	Increasing public awareness of nutrition	0.170	2.25	0.382
2	National demand for beef cattle is very high and has not been met by local supply	0.133	2.75	0.365
3	Profitable byproduct	0.115	3.5	0.402
4	As a food support	0.167	3.37	0.562
Sub Total		0.585		1.711
<i>(Threats)</i>				
1	Animal feed prices are expensive	0.154	1.12	0.172
2	Changing consumer patterns	0.162	1.25	0.202
3	The existence of competitors	0.094	1.87	0.175
Sub Total		0.41		0.549
Total Nilai (Sub Total I + Sub Total II)		1		2.26

Source: Processed primary data, 2023

The steps for compiling an external strategic matrix represent the opportunities and threats faced by beef cattle farming businesses at the Indonesian People's Animal Husbandry School Alumni Solidarity (SASPRI) in South Dolo District, Sigi Regency. Based on the results of in-depth interviews that the author conducted with breeders, a total weighted value was obtained, where the total weighted value is the total result of multiplying the weights by the rating of each external strategic factor. By entering the results of identifying opportunities and threats as external strategic factors, then giving a weight and rating to each factor. The results of the external strategic matrix analysis with 2.26 means that the external environment for the development of beef cattle farming businesses at the Indonesian People's Animal Husbandry School Alumni Solidarity (SASPRI) in South Dolo District, Sigi Regency is in a moderate condition and is not weak.

3. Eva Internal External (IE) Matrix

Figure 2. Internal and External Matrix (IE)

In Figure 2. Based on the results of the internal matrix and external matrix tables, it is known that the internal value is 2.512 and the external value is 2.26. Thus, the development of the beef cattle farming business in the Indonesian People's Animal Husbandry School Alumni Solidarity (SASPRI) South Dolo District, Sigi Regency is in quadrant V position, namely the strategy required for the current business is (Hold and Maintain). Hold and Maintain shows that the livestock business has a strategy to defend and maintain. The strategy obtained from the IE matrix is to procure quality feeder cattle to increase productivity in the beef cattle business at the Indonesian People's Animal Husbandry School Alumni Solidarity (SASPRI) South Dolo District, Sigi Regency.

4. Beef Cattle Farming Business SWOT Matrix

Table 4.4 SWOT Matrix for Beef Cattle Farming Business Development in Solidarity Alumni of the Indonesian People's Animal Husbandry School (SASPRI) South Dolo District, Sigi Regency

Table 4.4

Internal	<p>Strengths (S) Strength</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Breeding experience Quality beef cattle Short distribution channels Availability of feed land Breeder education (Nonformal) Potential natural resources owned 	<p>Weakness (W) Weakness</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> There is no processing of livestock waste products Access to technology and technological development is still low Limited capital The time for cultivating livestock is quite long
External	<p>Opportunities (O) Opportunity</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Increasing public awareness of nutrition National demand for beef cattle is very high and has not been met by local supply Profitable by-products As a food buffer 	<p>WO Strategy</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Resources owned to increase beef cattle productivity to meet local supply needs (S6, O2)
		<p>WO Strategy</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Increasing knowledge about processing livestock waste products, which provides profitable income (W2, O3)

Source: Processed primary data, 2023.

5. Priority Strategy for Beef Cattle Farming Business Development Solidarity with Alumni of the Indonesian People's Animal Husbandry School (SASPRI) South Dolo District, Sigi Regency

Table 4.5 QSPM for Beef Cattle Farming Business Development at SASPRI

FACTORSKEY	Weight	Strategy Alternatives									
		SO		WO		ST				WT	
		US	BAG	US	BAG	US	BAG	US	BAG	US	BAG
Internal Key Factors											
1. Breeding experience	0.095	4	0.38	4	0.38	4	0.38	4	0.38	3	0.285
2. Quality of beef cattle	0.088	3	0.264	4	0.352	3	0.264	2	0.176	4	0.352
3. Short distribution channels	0.099	4	0.396	2	0.198	3	0.297	3	0.297	3	0.297
4. Availability of feed land	0.077	2	0.154	3	0.231	4	0.308	3	0.231	2	0.154
5. Breeder education (Nonformal)	0.114	3	0.432	3	0.432	3	0.432	4	0.576	3	0.432
6. Potential natural resources owned	0.081	3	0.243	2	0.162	2	0.162	4	0.324	3	0.243
7. There is no processing of beef cattle waste products	0.117	2	0.234	2	0.234	3	0.351	4	0.468	4	0.468
8. Access to technology and technological development is still low	0.102	2	0.204	2	0.204	2	0.204	3	0.306	3	0.306
9. Limited capital	0.123	2	0.246	2	0.246	1	0.123	2	0.246	2	0.246
10. The time for cultivating livestock is quite long	0.094	2	0.188	1	0.094	2	0.188	2	0.188	1	0.094
External Key Factors											
1. Increase awareness people about nutrition	0.180	3	0.54	2	0.36	2	0.36	3	0.54	3	0.54
2. National demand for beef cattle is very high	0.132	3	0.396	1	0.132	2	0.264	2	0.264	2	0.264
3. Profitable by-products	0.120	4	0.48	3	0.36	1	0.120	2	0.24	1	0.120
4. As a food buffer	0.156	4	0.624	2	0.312	2	0.312	1	0.156	1	0.156
5. Animal feed prices are expensive	0.132	2	0.264	2	0.264	1	0.132	2	0.264	1	0.132
6. Change in buying patterns Consumer	0.180	3	0.54	2	0.36	2	0.36	2	0.36	1	0.180
7. The existence of competitors	0.096	2	0.192	1	0.096	1	0.096	2	0.192	1	0.096
Total Attraction Amount		5,931		4,417		4,353		5,208		4,369	
Order of Strategy Priority		1		3		5		2		4	

Source: Primary Data Analysis, 2023

From table 4.5 below, it can be explained that the best strategy that can be applied in developing a beef cattle farming business in the Indonesian People's Animal Husbandry School Alumni Solidarity (SASPRI) South Dolo District, Sigi Regency based on the results of the QSPM matrix analysis shows that strategy 1 has the highest score of 5.931, followed by strategy 2 amounting to 5,208, strategy 3 amounting to 4,417, strategy 4 amounting to 4,369 and strategy 5 amounting to 4,353. Thus, the sequence of strategies that should be carried out by the company is as follows:

- Resources owned to increase beef cattle productivity to meet local supply needs.
- Having feed land to provide the nutritional needs of livestock in the long term.
- Increasing knowledge about processing livestock waste products, which provides profitable income.
- Increase the use of capital and increase technological development to face future competition.
- Improving the quality of the resources owned in order to improve the quality of livestock products so that they can retain consumers.

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of research and discussion regarding the Beef Cattle Breeding Business Development Strategy at the Indonesian People's Animal Husbandry School Alumni Solidarity (SASPRI) South Dolo District, Sigi Regency, the following conclusions can be obtained:

1. Internal factors in the strategy for developing the beef cattle business at the Indonesian People's Animal Husbandry School Alumni Solidarity (SASPRI) South Dolo District, Sigi Regency, are human resources, financial conditions, production and management, while external factors are economic conditions, social culture, and technological level.
2. The strategy that can be applied in developing a beef cattle farming business in the Indonesian People's Animal Husbandry School Alumni Solidarity (SASPRI) South Dolo District, Sigi Regency is to increase productivity by utilizing available resources, technology and capital.
3. The priority strategy that can be implemented at the Indonesian People's Animal Husbandry School Alumni Solidarity (SASPRI) South Dolo District, Sigi Regency is to increase existing resources to increase beef cattle productivity to meet local supply needs.

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